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Harnessing Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Interest and Engagement in Learning Activities among University Students in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study harnessed artificial intelligence (AI) for interest and engagement in learning activities University students in Nigeria. The study was conducted using University of Abuja. The study adopted a survey research design. Three research questions guided the study, and three null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The population of this study consisted of 284 students, all of whom were from the 300-level in the Science and Environmental Education department, University of Abuja. The entire population of 284 students was used as a sample for the study. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire to elicit information from students. The data collected was analyzed using mean, Pearson's moment correlation coefficient, and independent t-tests. The findings of the study revealed a perfect positive correlation between artificial intelligence and students' interest in learning activities ($r = 0.660^{**}$). The finding also revealed a perfect positive correlation between artificial intelligence and students' engagement in learning activities ($r = 0.500^{**}$). Finally, the finding revealed no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university, indicating that many challenges militate against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university ($t = 0.977 > 0.05$). The study concluded that AI is an effective tool for attracting the interest and engagement of students in the university. It was recommended that university management should place emphasis on the use of AI since it piques the interest of students in learning activities. All students should be taught and encouraged on the use of AI to enhance their active engagement in learning activities. The university management should provide internet access, skilled human resources in the field of AI, and create more awareness of the uses of AI for students.

Keywords: Harnessing, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Interest and Engagement and Learning Activities

INTRODUCTION

Technology has a significant impact on learning because it makes learning more engaging, makes material easier to acquire, and encourages teamwork. Additionally, it enables customized learning experiences and equips students to meet the 21st century's digital expectations. A good technology used in education today is artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence (AI) is the intelligence exhibited by machines, particularly computer systems (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). Copeland (2024) opined that

artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability of a digital computer, a computer-controlled robot, to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings. The author added that AI is a developing system that is endowed with the intelligence processes resembling characteristics of humans, such as the ability to reason, discover meaning, generalize, or learn from experience. Halper and O'Donovan (2024) submitted that artificial intelligence (AI) is a set of technologies enabling computers to perform various advanced functions, including the ability to see; convert the vision to understand; translate spoken as well as written languages; analyze data; draw inferences and recommendations. Al-Qahtani (2019) asserted that AI is a field of science that concerns building computers and machines that can reason, learn, and perform various functions in such a manner that would normally require human intelligence or involve data whose scale exceeds what human beings can analyze. In the submission of Chen (2021), AI is a broad field that encompasses different disciplines, including psychology.

AI is also described as a high-profile application. According to Alqudaihi, Aslam, Khan, Almuhaideb, Alsunaidi, Ibrahim, Abdel Alhaidari, Shaikh, Alsenbel, Alalharith, Alharthi, Alghamdi, and Alshahrani (2021). The high-profile applications of AI include advanced web search engines like Google Search; recommendation systems like YouTube, Amazon, and Netflix; autonomous speech like Waymo; generative and creative tools like ChatGPT and AI art; superhuman play and analysis in strategy games like chess and Go; and interacting via human speech like Google Assistant, Siri, and Alexa. Today, the potential to enhance learning experiences, improve teaching methodologies, and augment academic outcomes has garnered significant attention. Fitra (2021) stated that AI systems allow students to learn with the help of education assistants such as bots. Fitra (2021) stressed that the developing educational system requires the world of education to adapt to technological developments to improve the quality of education, especially the adjustment of information and communication technology. Canbek and Mutlu (2016) posited that artificial intelligence (AI) helps human beings to learn better and achieve educational goals more effectively. Similarly, Wang and Xu (2023) noted that the integration of AI into the education system has the proven potential to revolutionize teaching and learning processes. As evidenced by Kumar and Aggarwal (2020), artificial intelligence (AI) tools also facilitate the development of innovative teaching methods, such as simulations, virtual reality, and intelligent tutoring systems, which enhance student engagement and understanding. AI tools for learning activities include Kahoot, Quizlet, Duolingo, Socrative, Edmodo, Grammarly, MATHia, Carnegie Learning, Turnitin, and Google Classroom (Edionwe, 2024).

Artificial intelligence (AI)-powered tools enhance personalized learning experiences, provide instant feedback, and facilitate administrative tasks, thereby creating lecturers' time for more meaningful interactions with students. Chiu Chai as cited in Canbek and Mutlu (2016) noted that artificial intelligence serves as a valuable tool in addressing various challenges in teaching practice, allowing teachers to work at their own pace. This fosters self-reliance and independence in their planning and teaching processes. AI-powered programs can make decisions, solve problems, understand and create natural language, and learn from data. Keppler and Snyder (2024) supported this submission that lecturers can use generative AI in a different of ways including development of lesson plans and continuous assessment. Generative AI tool, such as ChatGPT, are used to teach complex concepts more effectively. Keppler and Snyder (2024) further stressed that lecturers feel more effective with generative AI when they key into it for solutions. Use of AI tools stimulates the students' interest.

Interest is the unity of expression, manifestation of the inner essence of the subject and reflection of the objective world, the totality of the material and spiritual values of human culture in the consciousness of the subject (Omonovich, Honkeldievna, Sadikovich and Uktamovna, 2019).. Freyer, Bueller and Thorndike as cited in Omonovich *et al.*, (2019) viewed interest an activator of diverse feelings, as a structure consisting of needs and its own figurative sensuality of a person, as a feeling of uplift, mental arousal, attraction to the subject. Interest is also described as an active cognitive attitude to reality and a specific attitude of the person to the object, caused by the awareness of his vital significance and emotional attractiveness in the context of study, an interest is a subjective attitude motivating a person to perform a certain task. It is a tendency of students to become absorbed in an agricultural practice and continue it. It is a feeling or emotion that causes the attention of university students to focus on teaching

experiences in agricultural practices. Interest according to this study is a motivational variable and plays a vital role in education, particularly students' engagement.

Student engagement refers to a developmental process comprised of student thoughts, feelings, beliefs, and behaviors in relation to the schooling context and his or her life-long learning trajectory. It also refers to behaviours of students such as attention, compliance, prosaically actions, participation in academics and extracurricular activities. (Furlong, 2014). Students' engagement also involves their emotions or affect behaviours such as interest, identification, belongingness, positive attitude/valuing of learning, and cognitions including self-efficacy, goal orientations, regulation, investment and strategies for learning, beliefs about school, teachers and peers. Griffiths, Sharkey and Furlong in Furlong (2014) asserted that a students who is engaged student feels and perceives belonged, connected, and participated not only in the school setting but in all aspects of life as well.

Despite the importance attached to the use of AI tools in universities, observation has shown that there is a moderate level of awareness among students regarding the potential benefits of AI technologies in education. The students expressed concerns about technical difficulties, privacy issues, and the adequacy of training and support for AI technologies. The resultant effect of the scenario is a lack of poor students' interest and engagement in learning activities, which poses a threat to low self-esteem, increased stress, behavioral problems, and poor academic performance. It is against this background that the study intends to harness artificial intelligence (AI) for interest and engagement in learning activities among University students in Nigeria.

Objectives

The study sought to:

1. Examine the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' interest in learning activities
2. Determine the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' engagement in learning activities
3. Identify the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools by university students

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following questions:

1. What is the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' interest in learning activities?"
2. What is the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' engagement in learning activities?
3. What are the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in by university students?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between use of artificial intelligence (AI) and students' interest in learning activities
2. There is no significant relationship between use of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' engagement in learning activities
3. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools by university students

Literature Review

Effects of artificial intelligence on students' interest

Artificial intelligence has a significant role to play in the interest of students. Petrescu, Pop and Mihoc (2023) opined that students are interested in Artificial Intelligence due to its trendiness, applicability, and their passion and subsequently interested in the subject, the potential for future growth in academics. The students' expectations are mainly related to achieving the knowledge in the artificial intelligence field. They later get more interested in acquiring high-level skills than using artificial intelligence. Diantoro, Arainy, Soderi, Juwari and Sakti (2024) reported that the uses of AI tools for quality of assignments, length of learning focus, and class participation all significantly rose as a result of the results, indicating a considerable improvement in students' enthusiasm for learning. Uses of AI makes students feel that they

are more interested in their classes. Incorporating AI into education offers a lot of promise to boost student interest in studying, but doing so calls for a planned strategy and continuous assistance. According to Vieriu and Petrea (2025), positive educational outcomes are not guaranteed solely by the adoption of advanced AI technologies. The integration of AI tools in academic environments enables students to meet their unique needs. The students also exhibit improved self-efficacy and a more positive attitude toward learning.

Effects of artificial intelligence on students' engagement

The importance of AI on students' engagement in learning activities of student cannot be overstated. Many study have found the relevance AI tools in learning activities of students. Wang and Chen, (2020) found that AI-driven systems significantly improve student engagement and academic outcomes. The author added that AI tools are effective in enhancing learning experiences, especially in the creation of more personalized and engaging learning environments. Barata, Gama, and Jorge, (2017) found that when students who are actively involved in their learning process, they are more likely to perform better academically. As such, the integration of gasification with AI could provide a powerful tool for educators aiming to improve student engagement and outcomes. Li and Ma, (2021) found that AI tools not only enhance personalized learning experiences but also promote higher levels of student engagement by providing real-time feedback and support. Students who utilized AI-driven learning platforms exhibited marked improvements in their academic performance compared to those who relied on traditional methods.

Challenges militating uses of artificial intelligence

There are challenges affecting effective use of AI by students. Mustopa, Rikza and Hamidatun (2024) found infrastructure and internet access are the main constraints limiting the application of AI technology. Lack of human resources skilled in the field of AI, prompting the need for relevant skills development among educators. According to Asogwa (2024), the challenges facing the use of artificial intelligence are lack of awareness and understanding of AI, inadequate training and support, infrastructure and resource constraints, concerns about job displacement and bias, and limited access to AI-related resources. Jie and Kamrozzaman (2024) found that privacy and security, ethical considerations, over-reliance on AI and lack of awareness and understanding are challenges faced by students on the using AI applications to their learning experiences. A study conducted by Offor, Nwaru and Offiah (2024) found that excessive use of AI tools by students facilitates academic dishonesty, such as generating essays or solving problems without effort. AI tools may not fully understand the context of assignments, leading to inaccurate or irrelevant results for students. All these make them to perform below expectations in their academic activities.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

This study was conducted in University of Abuja, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey design. This design is suitable because the researcher collected and described the characteristics or facts about the population under study. The survey design also offers research subjects the opportunity to express their opinions based on their experiences, and the researcher could collect data from a small sample drawn from the population in order to draw inferences.

Population

The population of this study was 284, comprising all three hundred-level students of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja. These students were used for the study because they do not effectively use AI tools for learning activities.

Sample Size and sampling technique

The sample size for this study was 284 subjects. Multistage sampling procedure was employed to determine the sample size. Simple random sampling technique, specifically, balloting was used to select students of Science and Environmental Education, faculty of Education with a total number of 284 which was used as respondents.

Instrument

The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire to elicit information from students. The questionnaire had restricted response options of strongly agree (SA), agree (A) disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD) with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Validity and reliability

The instrument was validated by two experts: one from the Department of Science and Environmental Education, and Department of Statistics, University of Abuja. To ensure clarity, relevance and internal consistency of the items, the instrument was trial-tested using 300 level students of Guidance and Counselling department, University of Abuja. Single administration was done and Cronbach’s alpha was used to analyse the result of the trial-test. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 was obtained and was considered acceptable for the study.

Method of data collection

The data for this study was collected by the researchers, who administered copies of the questionnaire to students. The completed copies were retrieved at the spot.

Data analysis techniques

The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics. Mean was used to answer the research questions. The bench mark for this was 2.50 (4+3+2+1=10/4=2.50). The decision rule was: any item with a mean value of 2.50 or above was regarded as accepted while any item with a mean value of less than 2.50 was regarded as not accepted. Inferential statistics tools such Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient and independent t-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was: any p- value of 0.05 and above was regarded as significant while any p-value below 0.05 was considered not significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *What is the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students’ interest in learning activities?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Students’ Interest in Learning Activities

S/N	Item Statement	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	AI tools are user-friendly because does not take much energy out of you	2.97	1.04	Agree
2	AI tools can adapt to your needs and learning styles, providing customized content and pacing	3.19	0.74	Agree
3	AI tools interest you because you can sit and operate them at your pace	2.82	0.89	Agree
4	Interactive and multimedia tools can make learning more dynamic and interesting	2.93	0.65	Agree
5	Interactive and multimedia tools can make learning more dynamic and interesting	2.87	0.75	Agree
6	AI tools facilitate collaboration allowing you to share ideas	2.91	0.76	Agree
7	Interactive tools make the learning process more relevant and motivating for you	3.06	0.81	Agree
8	Digital tools enable you to access learning materials and participate in classes from anywhere with internet access	3.39	0.59	Agree
9	AI tools can be customized to meet your diverse needs	2.68	1.05	Agree
10	Using technology in the classroom helps you develop essential digital literacy skills	2.75	1.04	Agree
11	Using technology in the classroom helps you develop essential digital literacy skills	2.69	1.03	Agree
12	Exposure to technology in the classroom prepares you for the demands of a technology-driven world	3.13	0.87	Agree
13	By using AT tools, you can develop problem-solving skills, creativity, and an innovative mindset	3.08	0.83	Agree
14	AI helps to build your intellect	2.43	0.87	Agree
15	Digital tools enable presentation of video of practical skills	2.69	0.90	Agree
16	AI show you things you would not see during lectures	2.65	0.92	Agree
17	AI show you things you would not see during lectures	2.60	0.93	Agree
Grand Mean		2.87	0.86	

\bar{x} = Mean values and SD= Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results in Table 1 show that all the 17 items had a grand mean value of 2.87 and were above the benchmark of 2.50. This shows the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' interest in learning activities.

Research Question Two: *What is the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' engagement in learning activities?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Effect of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Students' Engagement in Learning Activities

S/N	Item Statement	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Personalized learning activities	2.89	0.89	Agree
2	Improves academic outcomes	2.94	0.49	Agree
3	Enhances student engagement in the school	3.12	0.54	Agree
4	AI makes learning more interactive and engaging through gamified content and adaptive learning platforms	2.88	0.89	Agree
5	AI to create interactive quizzes and simulations that respond to student input	2.90	0.83	Agree
6	Keeps students motivated and involved at all times	2.56	0.97	Agree
7	Creates active engaging and adaptive learning experiences	2.73	0.69	Agree
8	Creates active engaging and adaptive learning experiences	2.69	0.72	Agree
Grand Mean		2.84	0.75	

\bar{x} = Mean values and SD= Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results in Table 2 show that all 17 items had a grand mean value of 2.84 and were above the benchmark of 2.50. This shows the effect of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' engagement in learning activities.

Research Question Three: *That are the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in by university students?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Challenges Militating against use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) by Universities Students

S/N	Item Statement	\bar{x}_1	\bar{x}_2	\bar{x}_c	SD ₁	SD ₂	SD _c	Decision
1	Lack of awareness and understanding of AI	3.34	2.55	2.95	0.59	0.58	0.58	Agree
2	Inadequate training and support	3.13	3.55	3.34	0.79	0.69	0.74	Agree
3	Infrastructure and resource constraints	3.25	2.65	2.95	0.72	0.65	0.69	Agree
4	Concerns about job displacement and bias	3.18	3.75	3.47	0.79	0.69	0.74	Agree
5	Limited access to AI-related resources	3.24	2.54	2.89	0.68	0.63	0.65	Agree
6	Privacy and security	3.17	2.88	3.03	0.84	0.71	0.78	Agree
7	Ethical considerations	3.14	3.76	3.45	0.83	0.70	0.77	Agree
8	Lack of awareness and understanding of AI	3.26	3.64	3.45	0.66	0.62	0.64	Agree
9	Over-reliance on AI	3.08	3.85	3.47	0.87	0.73	0.79	Agree
Grand Mean		3.19	3.24	3.22	0.75	0.67	0.71	

\bar{x}_1 = Mean of male students, \bar{x}_2 = Mean of female students, \bar{x}_c = Cumulative mean, SD₁= Standard Deviation of male students, SD₂= Standard Deviation of female students SD_c= Cumulative Standard Deviation

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results in Table 3 show that all 9 items had a male students' grand mean value of 3.19, while the grand mean value of female students was 3.24 and was above the benchmark of 2.50. This shows that the items are challenges militating against the use of artificial intelligence (AI) by university students.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between use of artificial intelligence (AI) and students' interest in learning activities

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Students Interest in Learning Activities

		Artificial Intelligence	Students Interest
Artificial Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	.660**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	284	284
Students Interest	Pearson Correlation	.660**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	284	284

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The result in Table 4 shows *r* value of 0.660 at 2-tailed level of significance. The result is statistically significant. This means that there is a perfect positive correlation between artificial intelligence and students' interest in learning activities.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between the uses of artificial intelligence (AI) on students' engagement in learning activities

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the Relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Students Engagement in Learning Activities

		Artificial Intelligence	Students engagement
Artificial Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	.500**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	284	284
Students Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.500**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	284	284

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The result in Table 5 shows an *r* value of 0.500 at a 2-tailed level of significance. The result is statistically significant. This means that there is a perfect positive correlation between artificial intelligence and students' engagement in learning activities.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university.

Table 6: t-test on the Challenges militating against Effective use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools in the University

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	.024	.878	.029	282	.977	.00109	.03747	-.07268	.07485
Equal variances not assumed			.029	229.880	.977	.00109	.03758	-.07295	.07512

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The result in Table 6 reveals a p -value of 0.977, which is greater than the α value of 0.05. The result is not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university, is accepted. This is an indication that the opinion of the two groups of respondents did not significantly differ in their responses on the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that artificial intelligence (AI) has an effect on students' interest in learning activities. The test of hypothesis one also revealed a perfect positive correlation between artificial intelligence and students' interest in learning activities. The finding is not different from a report by Petrescu, Pop, and Mihoc (2023), who found that students are interested in artificial intelligence due to its trendiness, applicability, and their passion and subsequently interested in the subject and the potential for future growth in academics. The finding also affirms a report by Diantoro, Arainy, Soderi, Juwari, and Sakti (2024), who noted that the uses of AI tools for quality of assignments, length of learning focus, and class participation all significantly rose as a result of the results, indicating a considerable improvement in students' enthusiasm for learning. Uses of AI make students feel that they are more interested in their classes. Incorporating AI into education offers a lot of promise to boost student interest in studying, but doing so calls for a planned strategy and continuous assistance.

The study also found that artificial intelligence (AI) has an effect on students' engagement in learning activities. The test of hypothesis two also revealed a perfect positive correlation between artificial intelligence and students' engagement in learning activities. The finding affirms a report by Chen (2020), who found that AI-driven systems significantly improve student engagement and academic outcomes. The AI tools are effective in enhancing learning experiences, especially in the creation of more personalized and engaging learning environments. Also, the finding corroborates a report by Barata, Gama, and Jorge (2017), who found that the integration of AI into the university system could provide a powerful tool for improving student engagement and outcomes.

The finding further revealed that challenges militate against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university. The test of hypothesis three also revealed no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the challenges militating against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university, indicating that many challenges militate against effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the university. The finding agrees with Mustopa, Rikza, and Hamidatun (2024) who found infrastructure and internet access are the main constraints limiting the application of AI technology. The findings also agree with Asogwa (2024), who identified challenges facing the use of artificial intelligence as lack of awareness and understanding of AI, inadequate training and support, infrastructure and resource constraints, concerns about job displacement and bias, and limited access to AI-related resources. Similarly, the finding supports a report by Jie and Kamrozzaman (2024) that found that privacy and security, ethical considerations, over-reliance on AI and lack of awareness and understanding are challenges faced by students using AI applications in their learning experiences.

CONCLUSION

Interest and engagement are powerful motivators that energize learning, guide academic and career paths, and are essential for academic success. A student's interest in learning activities fosters concentration and encourages the diligent for advanced studies. The students who are actively engaged in learning activities perform excellently in their academic pursuits. The study has established that the use of artificial intelligence influences students' interest and engagement in learning activities. However, there are challenges militating against effective use of AI in the universities. The study concludes that AI is an effective tool for attracting the interest and engagement of students in the university.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. University management should place emphasis on the use of AI since it piques the interest of students in learning activities.
2. All students should be taught and encouraged on the use of AI to enhance their active engagement in learning activities.
3. The university management should provide internet access and skilled human resources in the field of AI and create more awareness of the uses of AI for students.

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